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Role of spirituality in the journey of recovery of persons living with Schizophrenia

Abstract: Spirituality is considered one of the important factors that contribute to the recovery experience of persons living with severe mental illness. Spirituality is a broader concept than religion, although religion is one expression of spirituality. Other expressions include meditation, interactions with others or nature, and a relationship with God or a Higher Power. This paper focuses on spirituality as a source of recovery from schizophrenia among individuals. Being one of the major contributory factors of recovery, the participants were inquired about their personal experiences of the role of spirituality in their journey of recovery. Recovery from severe mental illness is considered a subjective experience of an individual. It does not mean a complete cure or 'getting rid of the illness but is about staying in control of their life despite experiencing a mental health problem. Personal experience of recovery includes living with dignity, a meaningful and satisfying life, and hope for a better future, self-respect, and self-efficacy based on strengths, choices, and partnerships with mental health professionals and service providers. The study reported in this paper is conducted among eight persons living with schizophrenia. It discusses two themes related to the dimensions of spirituality that emerged as a result. One is connected with religion and the other is about an individual experience of nature. The study found that spirituality has helped participants to develop a great sense of meaning, peace, and hope, and to gain self-control, confidence, and self-esteem.

Keywords: Schizophrenia, Recovery, Spirituality, Mental Illness

Introduction

Mental illness is the leading cause of disability worldwide and is a major contributor to the global burden of disease (WHO, 2013). Globally, about 400 million people of all ages suffer from depression. Bipolar affective disorder affects about 60 million people worldwide. Schizophrenia affects 21 million and 35 million people worldwide suffer from Dementia (WHO, 2014a). Mental illness challenges human beings in two ways, firstly in the form of a struggle with the symptoms and side effects of treatment; and secondly, it challenges the person with stigma and prejudices, which is the outcome of ignorance and misunderstanding about mental illness (Corrigan & Watson, 2002). Stigma can be defined as "the process by which the

reaction of others put down the normal identity of a person or a group” (Goffman, 1963). Society’s reactions towards persons living with mental illness denigrate his/ her human worth. The employment opportunities of the person living with severe mental illness are bleak due to stigmatizing attitude of professionals, family members, and employers (Garskey & Stewart, 1999).

Schizophrenia in reality

Schizophrenia is a serious psychotic condition which is characterised by disturbances in thinking, emotions, motor behaviour, and relationship to the external world. This brain disorder affects the way a person acts, thinks, and sees the world. It is found that people with schizophrenia have an altered perception of reality, marked by a significant *loss* of contact with reality. Hallucination, delusion, disorganised thinking and social withdrawal are major symptoms of schizophrenia. It is believed that a combination of both genetic and environmental factors contributes to the illness; even though the actual causes are not fully known (Mäki, et al., 2005). Schizophrenia affects approximately 24 million people or 1 in 300 people (0.32%) worldwide. This rate is 1 in 222 people (0.45%) among adults, the illness is prevalent across racial and socio-cultural groups around the world. Worldwide, schizophrenia is associated with considerable disability and may affect educational and occupational performance. People with schizophrenia are 2-2.5 times more likely to die early than the general population. This is often due to physical illnesses, such as cardiovascular, metabolic and infectious diseases. It is more common among males (12 million) than females (9 million). Schizophrenia also commonly starts earlier among men.

Historically, the treatment of schizophrenia primarily focuses on symptom management and intervention comprises of medication, psycho-social therapies and rehabilitation. However, there is growing recognition that recovery from schizophrenia involves a multidimensional process encompassing not only the reduction of symptoms but also the restoration of personal identity, social integration, and overall well-being.

The current paper addresses the role of spirituality in the experience of recovery among persons living with schizophrenia through a qualitative perspective. The paper focuses on two sources of spirituality, religious as well as natural as identified by the participants of the background study. In this paper, we discuss what recovery exactly means in mental illness, especially in schizophrenia and its different dimensions. Dissemination of the concept of spirituality is also done for a better understanding of the concepts discussed in the paper. The background study of this paper is conducted among eight individuals attending rehabilitation services. The participant’s perception of the term ‘recovery’ and their experiences with religious and non-religious practices of spirituality and its influence on their current condition is also discussed in the results.

Recovery from Schizophrenia

The current literature discusses recovery from schizophrenia in two dimensions. One is functional recovery and the other is personal experience of recovery. Functional recovery is based on various criteria such as 1) symptoms not intruding in the everyday life of persons living with schizophrenia, 2) independent living where a person is able to manage his/her medication and money, 3) attending work or schools at least for

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half time, 4) maintaining a cordial interpersonal relationship with family members, 5) recreational outing with a friend or more and participation in social activities. Personal experience of recovery includes, living with dignity, meaningful and satisfying life, hope for a better future, self-responsibility, self-respect and self-efficacy based on strengths, choices and self-directions in treatment and social activities and partnership with mental health professionals and service providers (Lieberman, 2007).

The role of spirituality is considered one emerging area of interest which addresses the holistic nature of recovery from schizophrenia. The relationship between spirituality and recovery from mental illness including schizophrenia has invited the curiosity and attention of researchers and practitioners and persons with such lived experience. Spirituality, defined as a deeply held sense of meaning, purpose, and connection with something greater than oneself, has long been recognized as a fundamental aspect of human experience. Spirituality is discussed in terms of one's faith, belief, practices and values that figure in his/her life and worldview. Many studies have put light on the relationship between spirituality and recovery from mental illness. The potential benefits of including spirituality and religious practices in the interventions and treatment plans for mental health issues had been highlighted in these inquiries. The finding disseminated the specific role of spirituality in the inculcation of hope, coping strategies, subjective well-being and resilience building.

Spirituality and reactions

The reviews suggest that “Spirituality is a broader concept than religion, although religion is one expression of spirituality. Other expressions include prayer, meditation, interactions with others or nature and relationship with God or a Higher Power” (Burkhardt, 1989). The dependency on such higher power brings solace, guidance, and a sense of identity, particularly during challenging times. It also tries to provide a framework for understanding the nature of existence, the meaning of suffering, and the possibility of transcendence.

A study expressed that spirituality involves examining how we relate to the world around us and how we commune with our own sense of the divine. There is no ‘right’ way to be spiritual, and spirituality and religion do not have to be synonymous. At its core, spirituality is about what speaks to you, enables you to find meaning and purpose in life, and is a pathway to connect with power(s) that are bigger than you (Harren, 2022). Scientific literature strongly supports the notion that spirituality and religiousness can enhance health and quality of life (Loudet, Morgan & White, 2006). The studies show that higher religious faith and spirituality are associated with increased coping, greater resilience to stress, an optimistic life orientation, greater perceived social support and lower levels of anxiety (Pardini et al., 2000). Studies show that among persons living with mental illness, a higher feeling of spirituality can assist to reduce psychotic symptoms, improve social integration, lower the risk of suicidal thoughts and encourage adherence to psychiatric treatment.

Religiousness and practice of religion among persons living with schizophrenia

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The World Health Organization (WHO) considers spirituality, religion, and personal beliefs as important areas in the evaluation of quality of life (QOL) (Culliford, 2002). Many studies have evaluated the relationship between schizophrenia and religiousness. Even though spirituality is not only about religiousness, still these inquiries will put light on how religiousness as one of the sources influences their experience of illness and recovery. Studies also found that there are individuals practicing spirituality without religious involvement. The studies suggest that religion/religiousness in patients with schizophrenia is associated with better treatment adherence to psychiatric treatment (Mohr et al. 2011, Pieper, 2004). A study revealed that generous religious reappraisal was associated with better well-being, better adjustment, and lesser personal loss from mental illness (Philips & Stein, 2007).

Method and Materials

The background study for the current paper was conducted among eight individuals who lives with Schizophrenia for the last 5 years. All of these participants are in their journey of recovery, not actively symptomatic. They are attending rehabilitation services at two centres in Kerala, India. This is qualitative research with a case study approach (Yin, 2001). Eight participants were selected through a purposive sampling technique in which inclusion criteria were both men and women, only people living with Schizophrenia for at least two years are included as participants. Data was collected using an unstructured interview guide. The interviews were audio recorded with the consent of participants. The audio data were transcribed to text and coding was done. The similar codes were put together as categories and later, analysis was done based on emerging themes. The informed consent was taken prior to the study and confidentiality was assured as part of ethical consideration.

Results and discussions

Perception of Recovery

The perceived recovery from schizophrenia is complex and time-consuming. Moreover, living with schizophrenia is even more complex. Medical sciences determine that recovery from schizophrenia is perceived through multiple symptoms that individuals react with natural and reality versions of their perceived behaviour. However, there is no possible recovery from schizophrenia, but recovery in schizophrenia is a condition in which leading a life and doing daily activities without showing any symptoms. But the perception of recovery varies from person to person.

The participants perceived the term recovery as follows,

- A condition with no symptoms
- Getting cured of all symptoms
- Doing activities of daily living better
- Improving well in behaving with others

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- Gaining self-confidence
- Trying to seek a job, earning on their own
- Enjoying happiness and joyful moments of life
- learning the behaviour of seeking help from others
- Finding ways to recreation
- Gaining a sense of responsibility, for self and family

They perceive recovery as the complete absence of active symptoms. The perception of recovery as enjoying the joyful moments of life is an important quality because participants express that schizophrenia has decreased their ability to be happy for achievements. For many of the participants, recovery denotes better performance in activities of daily living; it also conveys a point that the ability to manage one’s own or independent living is a part of the recovery. Developing a sense of responsibility, and self-confidence, learning help-seeking behaviours, developing an interest to earn by self and finding ways for recreation are perceived as recovery. An important perception derived from the analysis is about receiving acceptance by society. This is an important perception because it reflects the significance of the role of society in recovery. This also means that recovery must ensure the integration of a person with schizophrenia into society. A similar finding was observed in a study (Mathew et al, 2023). Personal experience of recovery is been studied by the authors who found, ‘no symptoms’, ‘ability to work, ‘regain functioning’, and ‘emotional stability’ as perceptions of recovery.

Spirituality as a source of recovery

The data shows spirituality is a major component that provides a person living with schizophrenia a sense of well-being. Spirituality is a broad concept for inquiry but the analysis of data puts light into two major sources of spiritual experience. See table below.

Table 1 Sources of Spirituality

Religious sources	Sources from the nature
Reciting Rosary	Watching sea
Attending Holy mass	Watching rain
Attending prayer meetings	Spending evening time in the paddy field
Watching spiritual programmes on television	Scenes of birds flying in groups
Reading Scriptures	
Reading spiritual magazines	
Listening to religious speech	

All the participants follow some particular religion and they believe in God, the Higher Power. From childhood, they were brought up with values and religious faith. The participants strongly believe that God can change their condition and that Higher Power can see their pain and hear their sorrows.

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Table 2 The religion of the participants

Religion	No of participants
Hindu	2
Christian	4
Islam	2

The above table depicts the religion of the participants of the current study. All of them are practicing religion and have a strong faith. Out of eight participants, two of them belong to Hindu religion, four of them Christian and the remaining two belong to Islam

Table 3 Spirituality

Data point	Codes
<i>"When I pray Rosary or do my personal prayer, it makes me calm and I experience peace of mind. I forget my sorrows and believe that God knows everything about me. Nothing happens without His knowledge"</i>	calmness, confidence about life, peace, relief in sorrow
<i>"I feel happy when I do my Namas. I pray not only for me but for the entire world. It needs peace. When I read spiritual books and Quran, it touches my heart, having the power of miracles"</i>	Happiness, unites with the world,
<i>"The word struck me a lot, "I am the God who heals you". From that moment I got confidence and felt secure that God can heal me and it raised my confidence"</i>	Confidence, God
<i>"Future seems dark always in this condition but faith in God and in the providence can bring light to the future. It is truly my relation with God that gives me the courage to look at my future confidently"</i>	Security feeling, confidence about the future, God
<i>"Prayer of Peace is the most beautiful prayer I have seen. I pray it regularly, the words itself have some power of making us calm"</i>	Calmness
<i>"I like to go to the beach and my family takes me there sometimes. I like the waves coming and going. I feel every wave takes our sorrows away"</i>	Forgetting sorrow, relationship with family
<i>"I feel so happy to watch the rain. I used to sit at the entrance of the house to see it clearly. If it rains continue heavily I feel immense happiness in my mind. It takes away all my grief and tension"</i>	Happiness, taking away grief
<i>"I like to sit in the paddy field near my house. I go there every evening; from there I can see the sunset. The evening beauty of the sky and the birds flying in groups gives me a lot of joy. Nothing gives such happiness to me"</i>	Joyfulness, happiness
<i>"I read Bible daily; I get much relief when I read that. I have evening family prayer at my home, that is the time my mother and I pray together, it makes our relationship stronger"</i>	Prayer unites, relief of mind

The above table shows how participants reflect on their experiences of being spiritual. For them, religious prayer, scripture reading, and being with nature provide relief, calmness, inner peace, unity with the world, and a feeling of security. The participants claim that these practices connected with religious practices and

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nature contributes to the recovery experiences. Transcendence from the experience of illness to peacefulness in day-to-day life.

The current literature unfolds that positive religious coping has also been associated with a higher quality of life in the domain of psychological health (Philips & Stein, 2007). This finding goes hand in hand with the result of the study as participants express that their religious coping and faith are associated with their well-being.

Table 4 Outcome of Spirituality

The outcome of being spiritual	
Calmness of mind	Confidence about future
Confidence about life	Forgetting sorrow
Peace	Relationship with family
Relief when in sorrow	Overcoming grief
Happiness	Joyfulness
Unity with the world	Feeling secure

The analysis of the above data shows that the sources of spirituality provide calmness, peace of mind, relief from grief, strength to face the future, joyfulness, strengthened relationships, unity with the world, security feeling, confidence about life and hopefulness.

Conclusion

The current paper discussed the role of spirituality in the journey of recovery of persons living with schizophrenia. It was evident from the literature review that spirituality has an influence on the recovery experience of persons living with mental illness. Religiosity and other expressions of spirituality are examined in the paper. The results found spirituality instils hope to live and face life in difficult times. The participants consider their spiritual experience as a refuge in times of struggle. Religious or natural sources of spirituality help them to overcome the challenges that the illness place before them. Therefore, spirituality is considered a major component in the journey of recovery of persons living with Schizophrenia as identified by the participants. The research suggests that more studies on the factors influencing the recovery of people with schizophrenia need to be conducted. The inquiries such as the involvement of such factors in the treatment modalities also need to be considered for further research. Nature as a source of spirituality could be another area of exploration which will also contribute to the existing knowledge.

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